

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.6/

Optimised list of indicators

WP 1

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

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Technical reference

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¹PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
D1_6		DOMG and INSA	Created
D1_6 after review	21/04/2023	DOMG and INSA	According to MB comments
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Abstract

The current deliverable describes the process of preparing an initial list of optimised output indicators and describes the link with the operational objectives of the Partnership as laid down in the grant agreement. A list of output indicators with their characteristics is presented, including the responsibilities, baseline, target and timepoints for their assessment.

The added value of having output indicators is to monitor the performance of PARC throughout its lifetime. This will allow for a more efficient tracking of achieved goals.

As they provide the picture of PARC's achievements, they can be easily used across the consortium, by the different boards and partners of PARC to showcase and disseminate PARC's progress and contribute to a transparent monitoring of the Partnership under Horizon Europe.

Keywords

PARC, Indicator, output, outcome, impact

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Authors and Acknowledgments

The authors thank all the partners from PARC that contributed to this work with fruitful discussions and expert opinions, especially WP co-leaders and Task co-leaders for helping identify the most relevant monitoring frame for PARC activities and make the output indicators more specific.

List of abbreviations

AOP	Adverse outcome pathway
ASR	Annual Summary Report
AWP	Annual Work Plan
BMR	Biennial Monitoring Report
CSS	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	Governing Board
GO	General Objective
GSB	Grant Signatory Board
IATA	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment
IB	International Board
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MB	Management Board
NAMs	New Approach Methodologies
NH	National hub
NHCP	National hub contact point
OO	Operational Objectives
PSIP	Partnership Specific Impact Pathway
RA	Risk Assessment
R&I	Research and Innovation
SF	Stakeholder Forum
SO	Specific Objectives
SP	SharePoint
TL	Task Leader
WPL	Work Package leader

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

PARC is set up to consolidate and strengthen European public Research & Innovation (R&I) capacities in chemical Risk Assessment (RA). It has an objective-oriented structure and has been built with always the end-users in mind.

A number of Specific Objectives (SO) and Operational Objectives (OO) and the pathways to deliver the expected impacts (policy/societal impacts, scientific, economic) and related indicators have been identified.

On a wider scale, the report on the Performance of European Partnerships of the European Commission, also known as the Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR), aims to provide a strong evidence base to guide the implementation of European Partnerships under Horizon Europe and to inform strategic discussions on the effectiveness of the new policy approach to European Partnerships and, where relevant, how it should evolve. The report aims to shed light on the progress of these partnerships in achieving the EU objectives and targeted impacts both individually and collectively, at EU and national level. The BMR 2022 focuses on Horizon Europe's new partnership landscape and establishes benchmarks for assessing progress in future reports. To meet the goals set in the BMR, after intense discussion with the expert group, a list of Partnership specific impact pathway (PSIPs) and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was defined (Annex I; EC 2022).

Before PARC submission, a monitoring and evaluation framework was prepared, including a long list of KPIs that was used as basis for the PSIPs and KPIs table. Three different levels of indicators will be defined: output, outcome and impact. Briefly, output indicators intend to measure the amount of products (e.g., tools, materials, publications, etc.) generated in PARC; outcome indicators will measure the consequences or effects of the outputs produced (e.g., filled data gaps, uptake of NAMs by end-users; acceptance of IATAs); and impact indicators will assess the ultimate consequences of the previous indicators, e.g., in the definition of new chemical policy, or in the implementation of the one substance one assessment concept. All work packages and tasks provided input for the list of indicators. Furthermore, the discussions with the BMR expert group helped identify and focus PARC's story and enabled the streamlining of the PARC initial set of indicators to ensure not only their usefulness and representativeness but also the adherence of the whole PARC community to these indicators. The list has to be representative of what PARC wants to achieve while staying manageable and measurable.

The initial set of PARC indicators (Annex II) has been improved to provide an optimised list of indicators and will continuously be further developed and optimised in upcoming years to ensure the relevance and usefulness of the monitored indicators. Some of them were combined within the 12 developed output indicators as sub-indicators. Previous experience with indicators showed us that they must be useful to illustrate the progress and storyline of the activities implemented and that they should be relevant, while at the same time, not overtly time consuming to collect throughout the life of the activities.

The development and further optimisation of the indicator framework will be performed in collaboration with the PARC Management Board (MB), Grant Signatory Board (GSB) and the Governing Board (GB), National Hubs (NHs) and stakeholders, to ensure its relevance for evaluating the progress of the Partnership's key, useful and impactful results. More recently, convergence with the indicators of progress of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) was started, by interaction with EEA through meetings and workshops.

The list includes, for each indicator, a baseline and clear target values and will feed into PARC's Annual Summary Reports (ASR). A revised list will be produced in month 40, and published in D1.11 -Revised list of indicators, to be used for the mid-term review.

1.2 Objectives

The aim of this report is to present the improved set of output indicators and relevant discussion in its development, focusing on the baseline and target values set, and complemented with a more qualitative evaluation. The complete indicator set will supply an ‘easy to understand and interpret’ overview of the output, outcome and impact and will be a showcase of PARC.

1.3 Methods

A process of co-creation with the PARC WP co-leaders (WPL), task co-leaders (TL) and task members, was conducted. Following discussions among a core team from co-leader institutions, specific questions were directed at the WPL and TL relevant for each indicator. Feedback was provided and some bilateral meetings were held to clarify the indicator needs. Finally, the revised list was optimised by the core team. A list of the consultation steps involved is presented in Table 1.

In PARC, indicators are formulated on three levels:

Figure 1. The 3 levels of indicators in PARC.

The output indicators are an instrument to monitor the progress during the PARC project.

Outcome indicators will be used as an instrument to monitor the societal, political, scientific and economic effect of the PARC project. Each output indicator was considered to be equally relevant.

To monitor the impact of PARC on policy, science and society in the broad sense, we will use impact indicators.

Table 1: Overview of consultations undertaken in the process of output indicator optimisation.

Online Meetings with PARC Task 1.3 co-leaders and the PARC Coordination Team	Date
DOMG-INSA	19/10/2022
DOMG-INSA	07/11/2022
DOMG-INSA-VITO-ANSES	10/11/2022
DOMG-INSA-VITO	24/11/2022
DOMG-INSA-VITO-ANSES	30/11/2022
DOMG-INSA-VITO-ANSES	15/02/2023
DOMG-INSA	27/03/2023
DOMG-INSA	24/05/2023
DOMG-INSA-VITO-ANSES	22/06/2023
Mailings to all responsible partners for input on list of output indicators (DOMG + INSA)	
Bilateral online discussions with different WPs:	
-DOMG-INSA-EEA (WP2)	26/10/2022
-DOMG-INSA- NH coordinator (WP1)	14/11/2022

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-DOMG-INSA-EEA (WP3)	26/10/2022
-DOMG-INSA-EEA-NNK	08/03/2023
-DOMG-INSA- NH coordinator (WP1)	13/04/2023
-DOMG-INSA-RIVM-BFR-VITO	20/04/2023
-DOMG-INSA-NH coordinator (WP1)	23/08/2023
Presentation and discussion of optimised list of output indicators during the PARC MB (Annex III) for consolidation.	05/12/2022
Workshops	08/06/2023
Workshop on CSS indicators of relevance to PARC (presentation of PARC indicators)	

To be as useful as possible, indicators should be representative of the results expected, on the three levels identified below, reliable and require engagement from the PARC community in particular the MB and task leaders. This meant streamlining the indicator list, with those involved in their achievement and monitoring, to an essential list highlighting the progress towards achieving the objectives and showcasing the PARC storyline.

The Critical Risks list that may hamper the progress of PARC, which is part of the PARC Grant Agreement (GA, page 193), has been considered in building the indicators, so that the time of reporting each indicator allows for corrective measures before the end of the tasks. The relation of the indicator with the critical risks was considered in the description of each indicator. In case of any deviation of the target for indicators, corrective measures should be pursued by the responsible of each indicator.

The process of convergence with the indicators of progress of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability started in April 2023 through meetings and workshops with the European Environment Agency who is involved in building the CSS indicator framework.

2. Results

2.1 Preparation of the list of optimised output indicators

Starting from PSIPs and KPI table (Annex I), the process described above, based on expert advice regarding the most important indicators, together with the convergence with BMR and the objectives of PARC, allowed us to reduce the long list of KPIs (Annex II) to an essential set of 12 output indicators. In the next sections, the optimised list of indicators is presented in detail. For every output indicator, the link with the operational objectives and the risks describes in the PARC Grant Agreement (GA) was made. Not all indicators are already closed. Discussion on some indicators is still needed.

2.2 List of output indicators

A list of 12 output indicators is presented below. For each output indicator the following aspects are described:

- Responsible partner to provide input data for the indicator
- Data source to feed the indicator
- Baseline and target
- Timing of indicator reporting and updates
- Link to the PSIPs (operational level)
- Link to the Operational Objectives

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- Risks as described in GA that are tracked by the specific indicator
- Proposal for monitoring methodology

11. Number and characteristics of the PARC partners

Responsible	PARC Coordinator (ANSES)
Data source	Consortium agreement, GB, GSB
Baseline	N° at start of PARC: 199 partners from 28 countries, 5 EC DGs (DG RTD, ENV, SANTE, GROW, JRC) and 3 EU agencies (ECHA, EEA, EFSA)
Target	Growing no. of countries, Widen the coverage of PARC partners (EU coverage and expertise coverage)
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB November meeting)
Link PSIPs	Expand the cross-disciplinary network
Link with OO	OO1: Set up and operate a high-level group of EU and national representatives engaged in regulatory risk assessment and risk management, to strategically steer the Partnership
Critical Risks identified in the GA	Difficulty of engagement of the funders leading to insufficient resources allocations at national level and difficulties for partners to engage in the initiation, planning or implementation of PARC projects
Monitoring	N.º of new PARC partners Nº of new countries New partner's characteristics (indicate number of each type): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant signatory • Affiliated entities • Associated partner • Third parties giving in-kind contributions to the action • Subcontractors • Non-EU participants • Participants which are international organisations • Pillar-assessed participants

12. Performance of national hubs involving a broad network of stakeholders and engaged collaboration

Responsible	WP2 co-leads (EEA and EAA), National Hub co-coordinator (UKHSA, NPHC, SZU-SK)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio, National Hubs (NHs) surveys. Performance of NH will be tracked based on 4 criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP leader requests: percentage of response on requests: 4 different categories: Scale: 1 (<50%), 2 (50-60%), 3 (60-80%), 4 (>80%) • Questionnaires : Responded yes/no; percentage response • NH meetings (from NHCP questionnaire): Who participated, PARC partners: yes/no, GB representative: yes/no, GSB representative: yes/no,

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	<p>stakeholders (not directly involved in PARC): industry, NGO's, other (based on meeting repository)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NHCP meetings: Attended: yes/no/not scored -> attendance rate
Baseline	Based on response to First National Hub Survey (May 2022-Dec 2022)
Target	Will be further elaborated in collaboration with WP2 co-leaders
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in november)
Link PSIPs	Expand the cross-disciplinary network
Sub-indicators	<p>2.1 Response to WP lead requests</p> <p>2.2 Response rate to NHCP questionnaire</p> <p>2.3 Composition of National Hubs</p> <p>2.4 Number of NHCP meetings and attendance rate</p>
Link with OO	OO2: Create Expand a long-term sustainable network of National Hubs that interact with stakeholders to exchange and feed expertise, knowledge and needs into the Partnership and promote uptake of results
Critical Risks identified in the GA	Difficulty of engagement of the funders leading to insufficient resources allocations at national level and difficulties for partners to engage in the initiation, planning or implementation of PARC projects
Monitoring	<p>2.1 Response to WP lead requests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of requests send to NHCP Number of requests responded by NHCP <p>2.2 Response rate to NHCP questionnaire</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responded (Yes/No) Percentage of response <p>2.3 Composition of National Hubs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How many participants- Who participates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) PARC Partners ii) GB Representative iii) GSB Representative iv) Funding bodies v) Stakeholders: Industry vi) (those not involved directly with PARC) vii) Stakeholders: NGOs viii) (those not involved directly with PARC) ix) Stakeholders: Others x) (those not involved directly with PARC) xi) Others (State who) <p>2.3 Number of NHCP meetings (details from the NHCP questionnaire) and attendance rate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number that Attended

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number with Presentation given

13. Number and characteristics of science-policy communications

Responsible	WP2 co-leads (EEA and EAA)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio No. of actions: policy briefs published & overview of input to regulatory processes. Timeline with EU Board, GB meetings/interactions.
Baseline	0 policy briefs, 0 meetings, 0 input into regulatory processes.
Target	Will be further elaborated in collaboration with WP2 co-leaders
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)
Link PSIPs	Foster regulatory uptake
Link with OO	OO4: Actively foster the regulatory uptake of knowledge produced under the Partnership in chemical risk assessment and regulatory processes
Critical Risks identified in the GA	/
Monitoring	N.º of science-policy communications Science-policy communications characteristics (indicate number): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance rate Governing Board Workshop communication Media/press communication Radio TV Web communication Other (specify)

14.

Number and characteristics of synergies and collaborations with other relevant (R&I) initiatives

Responsible	WP3 co-leads (INSA, GCSL)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio, SYNnet and SYNnet Forum Reports
Baseline	0
Target	% increase of nº of synergies
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)
Link PSIPs	Build capacities and consolidate networks
Link with OO	OO5: Promote cooperation with other research & innovation Partnerships, programmes and activities across Europe and foster European leadership at the international level for research and innovation in chemical risk assessment

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Critical Risks identified in the GA	Duplication of activities with other ongoing EU or international initiatives
Monitoring	Number of synergies and collaborations with other relevant (R&I) initiatives (Synergie = signed contract or official collaboration; Collaboration = work with other partners (no official contract)) Indicate entity with Synergy /collaboration

15. Number and characteristics of interactions and communications with citizens and stakeholders

Responsible	WP3 co-leads (INSA, GCSL)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio
Baseline	0
Target	5 interactions per year with citizens/stakeholders; annual increase of website views/ social media followers
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)
Link PSIPs	Develop monitoring activities & implement FAIR data practices
Link with OO	OO3: Define common research and innovation strategies with transparent criteria and prioritisation process to address the regulatory knowledge needs for chemical risk assessment and management OO6: Effectively and transparently communicate and disseminate knowledge produced by the Partnership, ensure public accessibility to results and increase citizens' understanding and awareness of the principles of European chemical risk assessment
Critical Risks identified in the GA	/
Monitoring	Number of interactions and communications with citizens and stakeholders Characteristics of the interactions(indicate number): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder consultations/interactions • Surveys to stakeholders • Website views • Social media followers

16. Number and characteristics of projects approved for implementation

Responsible	PARC coordinator (ANSES)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio / AWP /ASR
Baseline	0
Target	% increase of projects contributing to OOs
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)

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Subindicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Projects contributing to OO8 (Develop monitoring capacity by extending the human biomonitoring platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes.) Projects contributing to OO9 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of the Partnership's results in regulatory risk assessment processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to risk assessment) Projects on working environment and occupational health Projects (re)using existing data (FAIR practises) <p><i>Keywords will be used to characterise the project</i></p>
Link PSIPs	Define and implement common R&I strategies
Link with OO	OO7: Develop and implement annual research and innovation work programmes on the basis of the 3-year common strategies
Critical Risks identified in the GA	No satisfying agreement on PARC priorities at EU/national levels because of high diversity of research questions or different regulatory agenda
Monitoring	<p>N.º of projects approved for implementation</p> <p>For each project, indicate characteristics (Classification NGRA, environment, human health, human biomonitoring, workers, monitoring methods, risk assessment, mixtures, health effects):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project's title/acronym Project's % of implementation (scale 1-100%)

17. Number and characteristics of scientific publications

Responsible	WP3 co-leads (INSA, GCSL), T3.2 (EEA, NPHC)
Data source	Available database on SP, bibliographic repositories and Annual Summary Report
Baseline	0
Target	10% yearly increase (to be elaborated further with WP3 co-leads)
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)
Link PSIPs	Develop and enhance innovative methods and models
Link with OO	OO6: Effectively and transparently communicate and disseminate knowledge produced by the Partnership, ensure public accessibility to results and increase citizens' understanding and awareness of the principles of European chemical risk assessment
Critical Risks identified in the GA	/
Monitoring	<p>N.º of scientific publications</p> <p>Scientific publications characteristics (indicate number):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paper in journal with peer review Oral communication (workshop, congress, ...) Poster communication (workshop, congress, ...) Paper in journal without peer review Book Book chapter

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other (please specify)
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18. Proportion of datasets developed in PARC that reach a predefined level of "FAIRness"

Responsible	WP7 co-lead (VITO)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio
Baseline	0%
Target	70-80% of new PARC datasets generated in PARC reach a predefined level of FAIRness by the end of PARC
	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)
Sub-indicator	New datasets generated in PARC being F(%), A(%), I(%), R(%)
Link PSIPs	Develop monitoring activities & implement FAIR data practices
Link with OO	OO10. Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA
Critical Risks identified in the GA	Production of non-harmonised or non-standardised data Difficulty to have access to some data due to availability issues or GDPR obligations for individual data sharing and due to ethical concerns Insufficient engagement for data management in different WPs
Monitoring	<p>Number of new datasets generated in PARC</p> <p>For each dataset as you are responsible for, characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset /acronym Dataset to reach FAIRness with Proportion of dataset that reach a predefined level of FAIRness (scale 1-100%)

19. Number and characteristics of entities in the risk assessment network catalogue

Responsible	WP9 co-leads (MU, ISCIII)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio
Baseline	Entities involved in HBM4EU as baseline for human monitoring, 0 for others
Target	number RA domains and 2 types of capacities mapped (laboratories versus monitoring networks)
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)
Link PSIPs	Build capacities and consolidate networks
Link with OO	OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new analytical, toxicological and fit-for-purpose networks of laboratories and research centres
Critical Risks identified in the GA	Lack of participation from European laboratories due to complexity of QA/QC or funding process
Monitoring	Number of entities in the risk assessment network catalogue

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	<p>Characteristics (indicate number of each):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBM laboratories • Air and indoor environment (including dust) • Water • Soil/sediment • (Eco)toxicology laboratories, • Food and feed, • Consumer articles, • Biota • Private laboratory • Public laboratories
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110. Number and characteristics of training activities

Responsible	WP9 co-leads (MU, ISCIII)																							
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio																							
Baseline	0																							
Target	increasing number																							
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB)																							
Sub-indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of exchanges of scientists • number of identified (and disseminated) existing training courses and opportunities • number of online training resources made available 																							
Link PSIPs	Build capacities and consolidate networks																							
Link with OO	OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical risk assessment related to the activities of the Partnership and in collaboration with other existing programmes																							
Critical Risks identified in the GA	Lack of capacity/partners capable of organising the training and securing co-funding for this activity																							
Monitoring	<p>Number of training activities</p> <p>Characteristics of training activities — for each</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 25%;">Type of training activities</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Number of participants</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Number of hours</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Online / in person</th> <th style="width: 20%;">% of participants satisfaction</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Course</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Lectures</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other (specify)</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Type of training activities	Number of participants	Number of hours	Online / in person	% of participants satisfaction	Course					Lectures					Other (specify)				
Type of training activities	Number of participants	Number of hours	Online / in person	% of participants satisfaction																				
Course																								
Lectures																								
Other (specify)																								

111. Number of new methods developed or enhanced (NGRA, NAMs, analytical methods,...)

Responsible	WP5 and 6 co-leads
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio
Baseline	0
Target	to be further elaborated with WP5 and WP6 co-leads
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB)

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Link PSIPs	Develop and enhance innovative methods and models															
Link with OO	OO9. Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for risk assessment and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake by different stakeholder communities.															
Critical Risks identified in the GA	Time needed for innovative methods development (NAMs, AOPs or analytical methods) might not allow a full implementation during PARC															
Monitoring	<p>Number of new methods developed or enhanced (NGRA, NAMs, analytical methods, etc)</p> <p>Characteristics of new methods:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>New or enhanced</th> <th>Published (yes/no)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>NGRA</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>NAMS</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>In silico model</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other (specify)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		New or enhanced	Published (yes/no)	NGRA			NAMS			In silico model			Other (specify)		
	New or enhanced	Published (yes/no)														
NGRA																
NAMS																
In silico model																
Other (specify)																

I12. Number and characteristics of monitoring studies (environmental and human)

Responsible	WP4 co-leads (UBA, SPF)
Data source	ASR including Project portfolio
Baseline	0
Target	increasing number of monitoring studies
Timing	Yearly (September — in preparation for GB meeting in November)
Sub-indicators	<p>Number of HBM surveys (per category: occupational, targeted, general population) + number of environmental (soil, water, air...) surveys.</p> <p>Sub-indicators related to characteristics qualitatively describing the surveys:</p> <p>Characteristics of human biomonitoring studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N of countries, • N of participants, • N of substance groups + biomarkers, <p>Additional criteria specific for occupational surveys with linked targets could be defined</p> <p>Characteristics of environmental monitoring studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N of countries, • N of matrices, • N of samples, • N of substance groups + substances + parameters
Link PSIPs	Develop monitoring activities & implement FAIR data practices

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Link with OO	OO8. Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes OO8b: Provide environmental and multisource data that address information gaps for regulatory purposes, within a collaborative framework				
Critical Risks identified in the GA	HBM surveys / institution to contribute to European monitoring survey leading to reduced representativeness				
Monitoring	Number of monitoring studies				
	Characteristics of monitoring studies				
	Type of monitoring studies	Number of participants	Number of countries	Number of substances	Number of samples
	Environment				
	Human				
	Other (specify)				

2.3 Link with Partnership Specific Impact Pathways (PSIPs)

As stated in the background, a list of PSIPs and KPIs for the 3 levels (operational level = output indicators, specific level = outcome indicators and general level = impact indicators), was defined with the European Commission expert group for the Biennial Monitoring Reports. This helped streamline the indicators and focus PARC's storyline (see annex I).

Output indicators are identified in the PSIPs on the operational level and are described in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Partnership specific impact pathways on the operational level

For each impact pathway there are one or more output indicators formulated that describe this pathway.

Output Indicators 1 and 2 describe the pathway “Expand the cross-disciplinary network”. Indicator 3 describes the pathway “Foster regulatory uptake”. Indicators 4, 9 and 10 describe the pathway “Build capacities and consolidate networks”. The pathway “Develop monitoring activities & implement FAIR data practices” is described by indicators 5, 8 and 12. Indicator 6 describes the pathway “Define and implement common R&I

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strategies” and indicators 7 and 11 do the same for pathway “Develop and enhance innovative methods and models”.

2.4 Link with CSS indicators

More recently, the convergence with the indicators of progress of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability was started, by interaction with EEA through meetings and workshops.

A **Workshop on CSS indicators of relevance to PARC, was held online on the 7th of June 2023**. The workshop had 106 participants including researchers from the PARC community, Member State experts and EU agency experts, with the aims:

- i) To inform the PARC scientific community on the ongoing work on development of indicators under the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability with emphasis on the link to PARC;
- ii) To discuss how the PARC scientific community can contribute to the indicator framework. Topics raised and discussed during the workshop are described in the report of the workshop. Following topics were discussed:
 - a. Spatial distribution — covering EU or indicators, not for signals
 - b. Extra indicators (ex. Drinking water)
 - c. Indicators based on environmental monitoring data
 - d. Risk based indicators vs. traditional risk assessment
 - e. Chemical load and link tot exposure and effect
 - f. How to group indicators

For the next steps, it was mentioned that the first version of the CSS indicator framework will be published in Q1 of 2024. After this, it is foreseen that the work on indicators will continue with development of new indicators.

There are some obvious connections and discussions on these interactions are implemented. All PARC boards are well aware of these and the idea of establishing links between the proposed PARC impact indicators and future CSS indicators is supported. Further discussions will take place to contribute to establishing these links with the aim of streamlining the PARC impact indicators and benefiting from the CSS indicator framework to highlight PARC’s contribution to policy.

A subsequent **workshop on indicators was held in Athens, 29 June 2023, with participation of the PARC GSB and MB**. The idea of establishing links between the proposed PARC impact indicators and future CSS indicators was well received by the audience and there was a real time attempt to find those links. For converging PARC impact indicators with the CSS objectives, there are some obvious connections and, since EEA is preparing a new set of indicators, it is a good time to discuss these interactions. Indeed, there was the suggestion to present and discuss further outcome/impact indicators in a next MB Meeting. There were some comments about the difficulties of measuring the impact at the end of PARC and even beyond PARC; another comment was that we should build on the HBM4EU data and indicators. There were also questions about the sustainability of these indicators after the end of PARC and we have also addressed this topic on the exit strategy (T2.3).

For further strengthening the link to CSS indicators, **EEA was recently invited to join T1.3**.

2.5 Reporting on output indicators

The reporting for the output indicators differs. Some indicators will have annual reporting using information from the AWP (11, 5, 6 and 8). Others will be reported every 18 months (synchronised with report to EC) (12, 3, 4, 7,

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9, 10, 11 and 12). Also there will be a focus of the mid-term (at M40) and final (M81) impact and performance evaluation of PARC.

We will try to have as much as possible the information on the PARC website.

- start of PARC: first list of indicators and project specific impact pathways
- initial set of indicators will be further developed and optimized (D1.8)
 - in collaboration with the MB, GSB and the GB, NHs and stakeholders, to ensure its relevance for evaluating the progress of the Partnership's key, useful and impactful results
 - Will feed into the annual ASR reporting
- D1.9: revised list will be produced on M40 to be used within the mid-term review + first performance and impact evaluation
- D1.19: M81: performance and impact evaluation to feed the final reporting of the project
- through the duration of PARC: feed into the biennial reporting on partnerships

2.6 Brief considerations on outcome and impact indicators

Based on the PSIPs and KPIs in the BMR, a list of outcome and impact indicators will be defined. The following phases towards their establishment by the end of 2023 are foreseen:

1. Discussion of the first ideas with the partners within task 1.3. (ongoing);
2. Proposal of an optimised list of these indicators and discussion with the European Commission. Discussions are also taking place considering how PARC results could contribute to the indicator dashboard being developed to measure progress under the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) (see 2.4);
3. Presentation and discussion in the different PARC Boards: MB, GSB, GB, Stakeholders Forum (SF) and International Board (IB);
4. Final list of outcome and impact indicators approved (by the MB).

3. Conclusion and perspectives

In the upcoming months, the final list of output indicators will be obtained to be presented on the PARC website and we will start with the detailed filling in of the related information. It should be noted that the list may suffer alterations along PARC development towards a more refined evaluation of PARC outputs and their relationship with outcome and impact indicators. The timing of the update of the different indicators is described in the presented list of output indicators. The output indicators will also be presented to the NHCPs, IB, SF, GB and GSB.

The list of output indicators will also be completed with outcome and impact indicators.

The full list of indicators (output, outcome and impact) will be presented to GSB and the GB, and stakeholders. They will be used regularly to present PARC's progress and discuss if they are still relevant and useful and if some improvements could be implemented to better serve the needs of the boards.

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We will also discuss with chair and co-chairs of the GB how to use the indicators as follow-up instrument for the GB.

4. References

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Performance of European Partnerships: Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR) 2022 on partnerships in Horizon Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/144363>

5. Annexes

Annex I – PSIPs and KPI table extracted from EC 2022

PARTNERSHIP FICHE: PARC

PARTNERSHIP SPECIFIC IMPACT PATHWAY (PSIP)

PARTNERSHIP'S KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

KPI NAME	UNIT OF MEASUREMENT	BASELINE	TARGET 2023	TARGET 2025	TARGET 2027	AMBITION >2027
RESOURCES (INPUT), PROCESSES AND ACTIVITIES						
Cross-disciplinary network	Number of partners involved in the PARC	HBM4EU	↑	↑	↑	All CRA disciplines are involved
Common R&I strategies	Number of projects/activities approved for implementation	0	↑	↑	↑	TBD
FAIR data practices	Proportion of datasets developed that are FAIR/partially FAIR	0	↑	↑	↑	100 %
Capacities and resources	Number of entities in the risk assessment network catalogue	TBD	↑	↑	↑	Sufficient coverage at EU level
OUTCOMES						
Active cross-disciplinary network for R&I prioritisation	% of countries that are actively involved in the network	28 countries	→ or ↑	→ or ↑	→ or ↑	100 % of countries that stay actively involved
Stakeholder awareness	number of activities that target stakeholders	0	↑	↑	↑	100 % of stakeholders that are aware and stay actively involved in CRA
Reuse of scientific and regulatory data	number of data set generated by PARC and reused	0	↑	↑	↑	TBD
Use of innovative CRA processes by public authorities	Number of public authorities which uses PARC output	0	↑	↑	↑	100 % of public authorities involved in PARC indicate benefit from PARC activities
IMPACTS						
Endorsement of CRA innovation in policy	Number of citations of PARC outputs/results in policy documents	0	↑	↑	↑	100 % of PARC policy recommendations considered by policymakers
Citizen trust in science and regulations	Number of activities that target citizens	0	↑	↑	↑	TBD
Support toward 'one substance one assessment' approach	Number of activities that contribute to 'one substance, one assessment' approach	0	↑	↑	↑	TBD

The contribution of PARC to the defined outcomes and wider impacts, and the activities implemented to maximise these, will be followed closely throughout the partnership to measure its performance and ultimately to provide a robust justification for the long-term sustainability of PARC's activities. PARC's impact pathway is defined in its monitoring frame to provide a qualitative and quantitative-based indication of the scale and significance of PARC's contribution to the expected outcomes and impacts. The initial set of indicators, including baselines and clear targets, will be further developed and revised regularly, with PARC's different boards and stakeholders, to ensure their relevance for evaluating the progress of the partnership's key, useful and impactful results and focus of the relevant target groups to maximise this impact and exploitation. The table above highlights some of the indicators at the impact, outcome and operational level.

Annex II — Draft long list of indicators at the start of PARC

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Objectives		Indicator No.	What is a measure of success?
<p>General Objective (GO) 1: Consolidate and strengthen the EU's research and innovation capacity for chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment.</p>	<p>Scientific Impact</p>	1	INTERNATIONAL RECOGNITION of the scientific network for research & innovation in chemical risk assessment - worldclass science
		2	Use of integrated exposure monitoring data for regulatory purposes
		3	Contribution of PARC to achieving healthier working environments
		4	Acceptance of methods, tools and models for use for regulatory purposes
		5	By 2030, all chemical RA data in Europe is FAIR
	<p>Policy and societal impact</p>	6	Sustainable engagement of European chemical RA community at international level
		7	Uptake of PARC outputs/results by policy makers/regulators at regional/national/EU/international level
		8	Contribution of PARC to EU and international policy strategies (SDGs, Green Deal)
		9	Workers, citizens and stakeholders' awareness about chemical risks and trust in science and how regulations protect humans and the environment.
	<p>Economic Impact</p>	10	Use of labo networks and infrastructural capacities by targeted end-users
		11	Collaboration with industry to ensure use and further development of concepts and toolboxes developed in PARC
		12	Participation of upskilled researchers in EU and international chemical RA networks
		13	Composite indicator measuring different aspects such as: Number and degree of attendance of academic and competent authority training programmes in areas relevant to regulatory risk assessment triggered by the Partnership. (Survey amongst academic and regulatory partners)

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SO1. EU and national risk assessors and regulatory entities come together with the scientific community in a cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for research and innovation in chemical risk assessment	<i>EU and national chemical risk assessment agencies and the scientific community enhance their collaboration and move towards 'one substance – one assessment' with shared evidence, tools and methodologies cutting across sectors.</i> <i>Synergies are established with other relevant activities derived from other the European Green Deal policy areas such as the 'Farm to Fork strategy', the 'Biodiversity Strategy for 2030', the '8th Environment Action Programme' and the 'Zero Pollution Action Plan for Air, Water and Soil', to understand and address their needs for research and innovation in chemical risk assessment and thereby ensure a better protection of .to better protect the environment and human health from hazardous chemical exposures.</i>	14	Sustainable engagement of national and EU hubs (whole chemical risk assessment community) on priorities for R&I in chemical risk assessment
		15	Established and widely recognised joint prioritisation process
		16	NEW: Increasing number of risk assessors make use of PARC outputs to align their work with the 'one substance-one assessment' objectives.
		17	Joint endeavours (uptake of results/contributions to PARC activities) resulting from established synergies with other R&I Partnerships, programmes and activities
		18	Targeted end-users communicate and disseminate about PARC results to society
SO2. European and national risk assessment entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint research and innovation programme to respond to the agreed priorities in	<i>EU and national chemicals risk assessment and management authorities rely on a sustainable Europe-wide research and innovation (R&I) platform for chemicals risk assessment, as identified in the Council Conclusions of June 2019 'Towards a Sustainable Chemicals Policy Strategy of</i>	19	Field-weighted citation index of peer reviewed publications
		20	Sustainable human health and environmental exposure monitoring network in Europe
		21	Feed into common understanding and definition of BoD calculations for chemical stressors
		22	Uptake of results on working environment and occupational health
		23	Use of methods, tools or models by targeted end-users
		24	Share of PARC documents/outputs actively used/cited outside of PARC

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<p>chemicals risk assessment</p>	<p><i>the Union' and in the 'Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability', to provide new knowledge and innovate risk assessment processes.</i></p> <p><i>Workers have improved protection and are better protected from chemical risks as set out in the 'EU Strategic Framework on Health and Safety at Work 2014-2020' through better insight into exposures and health impacts and improved safety measures.</i></p> <p><i>The Common European Green Deal Data Space is empowered by providing it with reliable, relevant, curated and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data on chemicals in line with the European Strategy for Data.</i></p>	<p>25</p>	<p>The GD data space is empowered by FAIR data generated in PARC</p>
<p>SO3: European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical risk assessment and communicate transparently to citizens and</p>	<p><i>Public authorities and industry engaged in developing a circular economy, including better waste management, as defined in the EU's 'Industrial Strategy' and the 'New Circular Economy Action Plan', are supported with innovation in chemicals risk assessment.</i></p>	<p>26</p> <p>27</p> <p>28</p>	<p>Europe has sustainable laboratory networks and infrastructural capacities supporting assessment and management of environmental and human health risks associated with toxic exposures</p> <p>Feed into common understanding and definition of concepts and toolboxes on EWS and SSBD</p> <p>Increased HR capacities in chemical RA? (No. and share of upskilled researchers?)</p>

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impacted stakeholders			
OO1: Set up and operate a high-level group of EU and national representatives engaged in regulatory risk assessment and risk management, to strategically steer the Partnership	29	Number of countries and EU entities participating in governance structures and activities and type of entities	
OO2: Create Expand a long-term sustainable network of National Hubs that interact with stakeholders to exchange and feed expertise, knowledge and needs into the Partnership and promote uptake of results	30	Number of active National Hubs involving a broad network of stakeholders and engaged in collaboration.	
	31	Number of coordinated activities involving national hubs	
OO3: Define common research and innovation strategies with transparent criteria and prioritisation process to address the regulatory knowledge needs for chemical risk assessment and management	32	Number of consultations for knowledge needs	
	33	Number of identified knowledge needs which PARC is working on	
OO4: Actively foster the regulatory uptake of knowledge produced under the Partnership in chemical risk assessment and regulatory processes	34	No. and type of science-policy interactions/ communications	
OO5: Promote cooperation with other research & innovation Partnerships, programmes and activities across Europe and foster European leadership at the international level for research and innovation in chemical risk assessment	35	Number of synergies and collaborations with other relevant (R&I) initiatives	
	36	Number of International Board advices and content of advices	
OO6: Effectively and transparently communicate and disseminate knowledge produced by the Partnership, ensure public accessibility to results and increase citizens' understanding and awareness of the principles of European chemical risk assessment	37	No. and type of documents in PARCopedia	
	38	Number of interactions with citizens/stakeholders	

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	39	Number of users or followers of the Partnership (including website and social media)
OO7: Develop and implement annual research and innovation work programmes on the basis of the 3-year common strategies	40	Number of projects/activities approved for implementation
	41	Number of scientific communications (including publications and bibliometric analysis; oral/poster presentations, scientific conferences)
	42	Number of (environmental) burden of disease and disease costs assessments for humans and the environment
OO8. Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes	43	Number of human biomonitoring surveys within the Partnership, generating exposure and effect data
	44	No. activities linking chemical concentrations/occurrence in environmental and/or human matrices to sources and pathways of exposure/health effects and risks
OO8b: Provide environmental and multisource data that address information gaps for regulatory purposes, within a collaborative framework	45	No. activities monitoring and/or modelling aggregate and combined exposures
	46	No. activities linking chemical occurrence in environmental and/or human matrices to health effects and risks
	47	Number of activities in support of the early warning system
	48	Application of prioritization measures for selection of chemicals and other actions
	49	Number of new methods/approaches proposed by PARC for acceptance as technical guidance

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OO9. Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake	50	Number of proficiency tests and round robin tests carried out
	51	No. New test guidelines No. Regulatory guidance documents produced
		No. of projects on working environment and occupational health
OO10. Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA	52	Proportion of datasets developed in PARC that are FAIR/ partially FAIR (F, A, I, R)
	53	Number of deliverables (re)using existing data
	54	Number of existing standards adopted for use in PARC
	55	Number of harmonised (meta)data schemes developed
	56	Number of novel methods from the computational field/data sciences implemented for use in chemical risk assessment
	57	Use of improved methods for uncertainty analysis and communication in Tasks ...
	58	Number of early warning signals detected by analysing data accessible to the Partnership
		Number and quality of catalogues for laboratory network, analytical methods, monitoring and population studies

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OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new analytical, toxicological and fit-for-purpose networks of laboratories and research centres	59	Laboratory network catalogue
	60	Analytical method catalogue
	61	Monitoring catalogue
	62	Population studies catalogue
OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for risk assessment and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake by different stakeholder communities.	63	Number of 'toolboxes' developed, based on requirements and performance criteria established through consultation
	64	Number of new models (in open access)
OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical risk assessment related to the activities of the Partnership and in collaboration with other existing programmes	65	Number of training activities (incl number of scientists exchanges)
	66	Number of junior scientists (PhD) working in the Partnership
	67	No. Scientists exchanged
Project Management Indicators: internal obligations/procedures in PARC	68	Timely delivery of the Annual Work Plans

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	69	Timely delivery of deliverables and milestones
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Annex III – Presentation at the MB December 2022

PARC MB meeting
5.12.2022

List of output indicators

Maja Mampaey
dOMG

Task 1.3 description in AWP1

Activities to be performed in the 1st year include to:

- PREPARE LIST**
 - Further develop the set of indicators originally developed in the Partnership's conception phase. This includes suggestions for baselines and clear targets for output indicators
 - Process the feedback of the EC's expert group on Partnership monitoring frames to further fine-tune the list of indicators
- CONSULT**
 - Process the feedback of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability towards a toxic-free environment indicator framework
 - Consult different PARC boards on the first set of indicators
- REVISE LIST**
 - Prepare the first revised monitoring frame and document on first set of indicators further to the consultations
- INTERACT WP2-3**
 - Interact with WP2 – task 2.2 on sustainability – for the development of surveys for sustainability indicators
 - Interact with WP3 on the preparation of easily interpretable indicator leaflets

1st list of indicators → ‘optimised’ list → ‘existing products’

PARC PSIPs + long list

HBM4EU indicator leaflets (22 performance; 6 impact)

Preparation of the list of indicators

- Teams meeting DOMG-INSA (19/10)
- Teams meeting DOMG-INSA (7/11)
- Teams meeting DOMG-INSA-VITO-ANSES (10/11)
- Teams meeting DOMG-INSA-NHCP coordination (14/11)
- Teams meeting DOMG-INSA-VITO (24/11)
- Teams meeting DOMG-INSA-VITO-ANSES (30/11)

Mailings to all responsible partners for input on list of output indicators (dOMG + INSA)

List of output indicators

1. Number and characteristics of the PARC partners
2. Performance of national hubs involving a broad network of stakeholders and engaged collaboration
3. Number and characteristics of science-policy communications
4. Number and characteristics of synergies and collaborations with other relevant (R&I) initiatives
5. Number and characteristics of interactions and communications with citizens and stakeholders
6. Number and characteristics of projects approved for implementation
7. Number and characteristics of scientific publications
8. Proportion of datasets developed in PARC that reach predefined level of "FAIRness"
9. Number and characteristics of entities in the risk assessment network catalogue
10. Number and characteristics of training activities
11. Number of NGRA methods and models developed or enhanced
12. Number and characteristics of monitoring studies (environmental and human)

1. Number and characteristics of the PARC partners

- Responsible: Coordinator - ANSES
- Data source: Project data, GB, GSB
- Baseline: 28 countries, 5 EC DGs and 3 EU agencies, 199 partners
- Target: growing no. of countries, better balance between environment and human health, keep partners engaged during and after PARC, which type of partners are involved in the projects
- Timing: yearly (from AWP's)
- Remarks: ok for ANSES, describe partners in different categories

2. Performance of national hubs involving a broad network of stakeholders and engaged collaboration

- Responsible: WP2, national hub coordinator
- Data source: project data, survey of national hubs
- Baseline and target: defined with subindicators (NHCC) and scoring system - see next slide
- Timing: every 18 months (reporting to EC)
- Remarks: discussed with NHCC

Baseline for indicator 2 - subindicators

1. WP leader requests: percentage of response on requests: 4 different categories
Scale: 1 (<20%), 2 (20-40%), 3 (40-70%), 4 (>70%)
2. NHCP Questionnaire
Responded yes/no; percentage response
3. NH meetings (from NHCP questionnaire)
How many participants (who participated), PARC partners: yes/no, GB representative: yes/no, GSB representative: yes/no, stakeholders (not directly involved in PARC): industry, NGO's, other
4. NHCP meetings
Attended: yes/no, presentation given: yes/no

3. Number and characteristics of science-policy communications

- Responsible: WP2 (EEA and EAA)
- Data source: project data (incl. No. of policy briefs & input to regulatory consultations)
- Baseline: 0
- Target: to be defined
- Timing: every 18 months (reporting to EC)
- Remarks: contacts with regulators and policy briefs will be produced by WP2; WP3 will disseminate those communication materials, will be discussed with WP2 and WP3 + task 2.2 - Parcopedia

4. Number and characteristics of synergies and collaborations with other relevant (R&I) initiatives

- Responsible: WP3, task 3.3 (NKUA and INSA)
- Data source: project data, including SYNnet Forum Reports
- Baseline: 0
- Target: % increase of n° of synergies
- Timing: every 18 months (reporting to EC)
- Remarks: evaluation in progress

5. Number and characteristics of interactions and communications with citizens and stakeholders

- Responsible: WP3 (INSA and GCSSL), task 3.1 (EAA) and 3.2 (EEA and NPHC)
- Data source: project data
- Baseline: 0
- Target: 5 interactions per year with citizens/stakeholders; 10% annual increase of website views/ social media followers
- Timing: every 18 months (reporting to EC)
- Remarks: to be discussed with EEA, EAA and NPHC

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6. Number and characteristics of projects approved for implementation

- Responsible: coordinator
- Data source: project data / AWP
- Baseline: 0
- Target: 100% achievement of AWP projects
- Timing: yearly
- Remarks: indicator includes subindicator:
 - Projects contributing to OO8
 - Projects contributing tot OO9
 - Projects on working environment and occupational health
 - Project (re)using existing data
 - Keywords will be used to characterise the project

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7. Number and characteristics of scientific publications

- Responsible: WP3, task 3.2
- Data source: available database on SP and Annual Summary Report
- Baseline: to be defined
- Target: to be defined
- Timing: every 18 months (reporting to EC)
- Remarks: bibliometric analysis? Promote to use journals used by regulators, meeting with INSA and EEA is planned

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8. Proportion of datasets developed in PARC that reach predefined level of "FAIRness"

- Responsible: VITO
- Data source: project data
- Baseline: 0
- Target: 70-80% at the end
- Timing: yearly
- Remarks:
 - subindicator: % of new datasets generated in PARC being F(%), A(%), I(%), R(%)
 - Discussion in progress with WP7 co-lead and task leads before confirming actual target

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9. Number and characteristics of entities in the risk assessment network catalogue

- Responsible: WP9
- Data source: project data
- Baseline: HBM4EU for human monitoring, 0 for others
- Target: number RA domains and 2 types of capacities mapped (laboratories versus monitoring networks)
- Timing: every 18 months (reporting to EC)
- Remarks: feedback from WP9 co-leaders received:
 - to be defined what "entities" are
 - identifying and bringing the capacities under one umbrella and covering all the relevant risk assessment domains
 - Definition on subindicators

10. Number and characteristics of training activities

- Responsible: WP9
- Data source: project data
- Baseline: 0
- Target: increasing number
- Timing: every 18 months (reporting to EC)
- Remarks: feedback from task 9.4 leaders expected

11. Number of NGRA methods and models developed or enhanced

- Responsible: to be defined
- Data source: to be defined
- Baseline: to be defined
- Target: to be defined
- Timing: to be defined
- Remarks: contact with WP5 and WP6 leaders

